

1 **Title: A combinatorial input landscape in the “higher-order relay”**
2 **posterior thalamic nucleus**

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4 *Abbreviated title:* Inputs to higher-order thalamus

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49

Abstract

50

51

52 Each one of the many pathways that target the thalamus terminates directly onto the
53 thalamic projection cells. As these cells lack excitatory interconnections, their
54 computations are fundamentally defined by the type and local convergence of the
55 extrinsic inputs. These two crucial input variables remain poorly defined for the “higher
56 order relay” (HO) nuclei that constitute most of the thalamus in large-brained mammals,
57 including humans. Here, we systematically analyzed the input landscape of a
58 representative HO nucleus of the mouse thalamus, the posterior nucleus (Po). We
59 examined the neuropil distribution of terminals immunopositive for markers of
60 excitatory or inhibitory neurotransmission, mapped input sources across the brain and
61 spinal cord and compared the intranuclear distribution and varicosity size of axons
62 originated from each input source. Our findings reveal a complex landscape of partly
63 overlapping input-specific microdomains. Cortical layer 5 afferents from somatosensory
64 and motor areas predominate in central and ventral Po but are less abundant in other
65 parts of the nucleus. Excitatory inputs from the trigeminal complex, dorsal column
66 nuclei, spinal cord and superior colliculus as well as inhibitory terminals from anterior
67 pretectal nucleus and zona incerta are each abundant in specific Po regions and absent
68 from others. Cortical layer 6 and reticular thalamic nucleus terminals are evenly
69 distributed across Po. Integration of specific input motifs by particular cell
70 subpopulations may be commonplace within HO nuclei, and favor the emergence of
71 computationally specialized input-output subnetworks.

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Significance statement

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75 Because thalamic projection neurons lack local interconnections, their output is
76 determined by the kind and convergence of the long-range inputs that they receive.
77 There is evidence that these parameters vary markedly within the “higher order” (HO)
78 nuclei that constitute much of the thalamus, but they have never been systematically
79 analyzed. Here, we mapped the origin and local convergence of all the extrinsic inputs
80 reaching the Posterior nucleus, a typical HO nucleus of the mouse thalamus by
81 combining multiple neuropil labeling and axon tracing methods. We report a complex
82 mosaic of partly overlapping input-specific domains within Po. Integration of diverse
83 input motifs by thalamic cell subpopulations may be the norm in HO nuclei, favoring
84 the emergence of computationally specialized thalamocortical subnetworks.

Introduction

85

86

87 The thalamus receives direct connections from an astonishing variety of systems,
88 from the cerebral cortex and retina to the caudal spinal cord. Remarkably, such input
89 pathways terminate directly onto the same projection cells whose axons carry the
90 thalamus output signals. Because the projection cells lack local recurrent excitatory
91 connectivity, output signals are essentially determined by the inputs that each cell
92 receives. Delineating input “motifs” is thus essential to understanding thalamus coding
93 and its overall role in cortical function (Acsady, 2017; Halassa and Sherman, 2019).

94 The input motif in the so-called “first-order relay” (FO; Sherman and Guillery, 1996)
95 nuclei is relatively simple and consistent across nuclei. FO neurons invariably receive
96 focal, topographic and synaptically powerful glutamatergic synapses from a single
97 source (a sensory or cerebellar pathway), and transmission of this “driver” signal is
98 modulated by abundant but weaker synapses from cortical layer (L)6 (glutamatergic)
99 and thalamic reticular nucleus (TRN; GABAergic; Pinault, 2004; Reichova and
100 Sherman, 2004).

101 In contrast, there is evidence that input motifs may be highly diverse and region-
102 specific in the remainder of the thalamus nuclei, referred to as “higher order relay”
103 nuclei (HO; Sherman and Guillery, 1996). As in the FO nuclei, neurons in HO nuclei
104 receive modulatory L6 and TRN inputs but, in addition, they receive many or all of their
105 “driver” inputs from cortical L5 cells (Reichova and Sherman, 2004; Mease et al.,
106 2016). The L5 axon terminals may converge onto the same thalamic cells from separate
107 cortical areas (Sampathkumar et al., 2021). The L5 inputs can also converge with one or
108 more synaptically powerful inputs from subcortical sensory and /or motor structures
109 (Groenewegen et al., 1990; Parent and Hazrati, 1995; Stepniewska et al., 2000; Bartho
110 et al., 2002; Bokor et al., 2005; Jones, 2007; Rovo et al., 2012; Groh et al., 2014;
111 Bickford et al., 2015; Timbie et al., 2020). Differences in the strength/structure of the
112 various input synapses as well as in the neurotransmitters they release
113 (excitatory/inhibitory) may further expand the range of variation among motifs (Halassa
114 and Acsady, 2016; Acsady, 2017). As a result of their diverse input motifs, thalamic
115 cells perform input-output computations in region-specific manner (Trageser and Keller,
116 2004; Lavallee et al., 2005; Groh et al., 2014; Ahissar and Oram, 2015; Halassa and
117 Acsady, 2016).

118 The input landscape is thus key to understand the functional organization of the HO
119 nuclei. However, each input system has largely been investigated in isolation, and a
120 cohesive picture is missing, even for the best studied nuclei. Thus, we set out to map the
121 sources, intranuclear distribution and axon varicosity sizes (as a proxy for synaptic
122 strength) of all inputs reaching the Posterior (Po) nucleus, a representative and
123 extensively studied HO nucleus of the rodent thalamus.

124 The Po nucleus has been reported to receive L5b input from the primary
125 somatosensory area (S1; Bourassa et al., 1995; Veinante et al., 2000a; Grant et al.,
126 2012; Sumser et al., 2017; Hayashi et al., 2021), secondary somatosensory area (S2;
127 Liao et al., 2010), and the motor cortex (Rouiller et al., 1991; Prasad et al., 2020). These
128 L5 inputs drive Po cell firing with high efficacy (Reichova and Sherman, 2004). In
129 addition, Po receives spinal trigeminal nucleus (Jacquin et al., 1989; Pierret et al., 2000;
130 Veinante et al., 2000b), dorsal column nuclei (DCN; Lund and Webster, 1967), spinal
131 cord (Iwata et al., 1992; Gauriau and Bernard, 2004) and superior colliculus inputs
132 (Gharaei et al., 2020) which are also able, under certain conditions, to drive Po cell
133 spiking. In addition, many Po cells receive inputs from the zona incerta (ZI; Power et
134 al., 1999; Bartho et al., 2002) and the anterior pretectal nucleus (APT; Bokor et al.,
135 2005), which provide strong, focal, and temporally precise inhibition (Halassa and
136 Acsady, 2016).

137 We show that the Po neuropil is a heterogeneous tridimensional mosaic of partly
138 overlapping input domains and suggest that thalamic cells in different parts of this
139 nucleus may perform fundamentally different computations.

140

Materials and Methods

141

142

143 *Animals*

144 Experiments were performed on adult (60-120 days old, 25-35 g body weight) wild-
145 type C57BL/6 mice of both sexes. Animals were bred in the Animal Facilities of the
146 School of Medicine of the Autónoma de Madrid University. All procedures involving
147 animals were conducted under protocols approved by the university Ethics Committee
148 and the competent Regional Government agency (PROEX175/16), in accordance with
149 the European Community Council Directive 2010/63/UE. Animals were housed under
150 standard colony conditions with food and water *ad libitum* under a 12 h light/dark cycle.
151 Efforts were made to minimize the number of animals required. In total, twenty-six
152 mice were used for retrograde tracing experiments, fifty-two were used for anterograde
153 BDA axon labeling and five further mice were used for immunohistochemistry.

154 In addition, the brains from two mice from the L5 Cre-expressing Rbp4-Cre: Ai14
155 strain (Gong et al., 2007) were used to examine the distribution of cortical L5 pyramidal
156 cell axons within Po. Procedures to obtain these two brains were performed in the
157 animal facilities of the University of Oxford (UK) under Animals (Scientific
158 Procedures) Act 1986 project license with local ethical approval by the Central
159 Committee on Animal Care and Ethical Review (ACER) and the Animal Welfare and
160 Ethical Review Body (AWERB) at the University of Oxford.

161 Tg(Rbp4cre)KL100Gsat/Mmucd (Rbp4-Cre; Jackson Laboratories) mice were crossed
162 with B6;129S6-Gt(ROSA)26Sortm14(CAG-tdTomato)Hze/J (Ai14) to constitutively
163 drive fluorescent protein expression in cortical L5 pyramidal neurons (Hoerder-
164 Suabedissen et al., 2018; Hayashi et al., 2021).

165

166 *Anesthetic procedures*

167 In the tracing experiments with post-injection survival, anesthesia was induced with
168 an intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (0.075 mg/g body weight) + xylazine (0.02
169 mg/g body weight), and subsequently maintained throughout the surgical procedure
170 with isoflurane in oxygen (0.5–1 %). At the end of the surgery, isoflurane was
171 interrupted, and animals recovered promptly. Ibuprofen (120 mg/L) was added to the
172 drinking water to ensure analgesia during the post-operative period.

173 At the time of sacrifice, animals were overdosed with sodium pentobarbital (0.09
174 mg/g body weight, i.p.).

175

176 ***Retrograde axonal tracer experiments***

177 Retrograde tracers were microinjected in the thalamus to map across the brain and
178 spinal cord the neuronal populations targeting specific thalamic nuclei. Animals were
179 positioned in a stereotaxic apparatus (David Kopf Instruments, Tujunga, CA, USA) and
180 placed on a water-heated pad at 37 °C. The scalp was sectioned at the midline and
181 retracted, and small craniotomies were opened in the parietal bones. Two different
182 retrograde fluorescent tracers, one in each hemisphere, were injected through
183 borosilicate glass micropipettes (WPI, Sarasota, FL, USA; outer tip diameter: 10–15
184 µm), positioned under stereotaxic guidance either in Po (bregma -1.8 mm posterior, 1.2
185 mm lateral, and 3.2 mm ventral; Paxinos and Franklin, 2012) or in VPM (-1.7, 1.7 and
186 3.3 mm, respectively). Fast Blue (FB; diamidino compound 253/50, Polysciences
187 Europe GmbH, Eppelheim, Germany; 0.1 % w/vol. in 0.1 M cacodylate buffer; pH 7.4)
188 or Fluoro-Gold (FG; hydroxystilbamidine methanesulfonate H-22845, Molecular
189 Probes Fluorochrome LLC, Denver, CO, USA; 0.75 % w/vol. in 0.1 M phosphate
190 buffer, PB) were used as tracers. FB was pressure-injected (0.01–0.1 µl) using a
191 precision electro-valve system (Picospritzer II, Parker Hannifin, Cleveland, OH, USA)
192 while FG was microiontophoresized with a Midgard Precision Current Source Cat N°.
193 51590 (Stoelting, Wood Dale, IL, USA) by applying 4–5 µA positive continuous
194 current cycles (7 s on/off) for 3–5 min. Pipettes were left in place for 10 minutes after
195 the injection, before being removed. Finally, muscle and skin were disinfected with
196 povidone iodine and sutured, and the animals were allowed to recover and returned to
197 their cage.

198

199 ***Anterograde axonal transport experiments***

200 To label axon terminals from the neuronal populations in various brain and spinal
201 cord structures identified by the retrograde tracing experiments, lysine-fixable 10 kDa
202 biotinylated dextran amine (BDA; Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA; 3 % w/v solution in
203 0.01 M PB, pH 7.4) was selectively iontophoretically injected in different regions of the
204 forebrain, brainstem or spinal cord. A positive current was applied using a Dual Current

205 260 source (World Precision Instruments, WPI, FL, USA) or Midgard Current Source
206 (Stoelting). Injection parameters are summarized in Table 1.

207 Forebrain regions were targeted following the stereotaxic coordinates of Paxinos and
208 Franklin (2012) atlas. To target the Gracilis (Gr) and Cuneatus (Cu) nuclei, the head
209 was secured in ventroflexed position. After a skin incision, the muscles of the back of
210 the neck were dissected laterally from the midline, and the atlantooccipital membrane
211 was opened to expose the dorsum of the lower medulla. The micropipette was inserted
212 in Gr or Cu (between 0.2 and 0.5 mm caudal to the obex). To inject BDA in the spinal
213 cord, a midline skin incision was made over the upper thoracic vertebrae. The
214 paravertebral muscles were separated and retracted, the ligamenta flava incised and the
215 micropipette tip was lowered into the spinal cord. After injections, micropipettes were
216 left in place for 10 min before removal and wound closure.

217

218 (-----(*Insert Table 1 about here*)-----)

219

220 ***Tissue fixation and histological procedures***

221 Animals were allowed to survive for 7 days and were then perfused transcardially
222 with 30 ml of saline, followed by 100 ml of 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA; diluted in 0.1
223 M PB, pH 7.4). Brains were then removed from the skull and postfixed overnight at 4°C
224 in the same solution, and cryoprotected by embedding in 30 % sucrose in 0.1 M PB, at 4
225 °C, for 48 hrs. In retrograde transport experiments, the whole spinal cord was extracted
226 and processed likewise.

227 In the retrograde fluorescent labeling experiments, three parallel series of 50 µm-
228 thick coronal sections of the forebrain, brainstem and spinal cord were obtained on a
229 freezing microtome (SM 2400; Leica, Germany). One series was mounted onto gelatin-
230 coated glass slides, air dried, dehydrated in graded ethanol, defatted in xylene and
231 coverslipped with DePex (Serva, Heidelberg, Germany). These sections were analyzed
232 under an epifluorescence light microscope (Eclipse 600; Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) for
233 retrograde labeling analysis. The second series was histochemically stained for
234 cytochrome oxidase activity (CyO; Wong-Riley et al., 1978) to help cytoarchitectonic
235 localization of the labeling. The third series was stored at -20 °C as a backup.

236 In the BDA axonal labeling experiments, brains were freeze-sectioned in the coronal
237 plane at 60 µm, and sections were collected in two parallel series. In the first, after

238 peroxidase activity blocking by incubation in H₂O₂ 0.66 % (w/vol.) in 0.1M PB for 15
239 min, sections were incubated for 2 hrs. in avidin-biotin-peroxidase (1:100; Vectastain
240 Elite™, Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA) diluted in 0.1M PB. After
241 washing, peroxidase was visualized using the glucose oxidase-3-3'diaminobenzidine
242 (DAB; Sigma Aldrich) nickel sulfate-enhanced method (Shu et al., 1988). These
243 sections were then counterstained with CyO histochemistry (Wong-Riley et al., 1978)
244 for cytoarchitectonic localization of the labeling. Sections were finally mounted and
245 coverslipped as above. A second series was used either for immunolabeling as
246 explained below or were kept in antifreeze solution at -20 °C as a backup.

247

248 (-----(*Insert Table 2 about here*)-----)

249

250 ***Immunolabeling***

251 All antibodies used in this study are commercially available and their host species,
252 manufacturer, and dilutions are indicated in Table 2. Immunohistochemistry against
253 vesicular glutamate transporter type 1 (vGLUT1), type 2 (vGLUT2) or gamma-
254 aminobutyric acid (GABA) was performed in some brains. Following peroxidase
255 activity blockage, sections were serially incubated in: a) 2 % Triton X-100® (Sigma-
256 Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) + 5 % normal goat serum (NGS) + 1 % bovine serum
257 albumin (BSA) in 0.1 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at room temperature (RT) for
258 2 hrs.; b) guinea pig anti-vGLUT1, guinea pig anti-vGLUT2 or rabbit anti-GABA
259 polyclonal antibodies (Table 2), 2 % Triton X-100, 5 % NGS and 1 % BSA in 0.1M
260 PBS with at 4 °C for 48 hrs.; c) biotinylated goat anti-guinea pig or goat anti-rabbit IgG,
261 2 % Triton X-100, 5 % NGS in 0.1M PBS at RT for 2 hrs.; d) in ABC Elite (Vector
262 Laboratories) 1:100 in 0.1M PBS containing 2 % Triton X-100 at RT for 2 hrs. Multiple
263 PBS rinses were intercalated between the above solutions. Finally, peroxidase activity
264 was made visible using the glucose oxidase-diaminobenzidine method (Shu et al.,
265 1988). In experiments involving immunolabeling against GABA, sections were pre-
266 treated for antigen retrieval in sodium borohydride 1 % (w/vol.) for 30 min, RT.

267 For some experiments, simple or double immunofluorescence labeling was
268 performed, in different combinations. The following antibodies were applied (Table 2):
269 guinea pig anti-vGLUT2, rabbit anti-biotin and two different rabbit anti-glutamate
270 decarboxylase 65 & 67 (GAD65/67). Besides, in tissue sections from the Rbp4-

271 Cre: Ai14 brains, a rabbit anti-red fluorescent protein (RFP) antiserum that also reacts
272 against tdTomato was used.

273 In experiments involving immunolabeling against GAD65/67, sections were pre-
274 treated for antigen retrieval in sodium borohydride 1 % (w/vol.) for 30 min, RT. In all
275 experiments, sections were incubated, free-floating, in 2 % Triton X-100® and 5 %
276 NGS in 0.1M PB, 2 hrs., RT, rinsed in PB, and subsequently incubated in the pre-
277 incubation solution plus the primary antibodies listed above (72 hrs., 4°C). Following
278 multiple rinses, sections were then incubated in the corresponding secondary
279 AlexaFluor-conjugated antibody (Table 2) in 0.1M PB containing 2 % Triton X-100 and
280 5 % NGS, 2 hrs., RT.

281 After rinsing in 0.1M PB, sections were finally mounted onto gelatin-coated glass
282 slides, air dried, dehydrated graded ethanol, defatted in xylene and coverslipped with
283 DePex (Serva).

284

285 ***Retrograde labeling analysis***

286 The distribution of the cells revealed by retrograde tracer labeling was examined
287 under an epifluorescence microscope Eclipse E600 (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) and mapped
288 on JPEG images of the serial sections acquired with a Nikon DMA1200 digital camera
289 and a motorized microscope stage (Proscan, Prior Scientific Instruments, Cambridge,
290 UK) controlled by the Nis-Elements® BR 3.2 software (Nikon). Images were
291 assembled into a single panoramic view using the Grab Large Image package of Nis-
292 Elements® BR 3.2 software.

293 First, we analyzed the location of the tracer deposits in the thalamus. 40X images of
294 all sections containing the tracer deposit (spaced 150 µm) were examined to delineate
295 the deposit consistently. For each deposit, we outlined a core zone of solid, heavy
296 fluorescence where no individual cell profiles were evident. Results suggest tracer
297 uptake occurred mostly within this zone. Nevertheless, for a conservative interpretation
298 of the labeling results, we also delineated and included in our analysis the peripheral
299 halo of fainter fluorescence where individual labeled cell profiles were visible (see
300 Figure 5). Retrograde tracer deposits were redrawn using the vectorial design software
301 Canvas® X (ACD Systems, Victoria, Canada).

302 Retrogradely labeled cell somata were subsequently mapped across the brain and
303 spinal cord. One out of six coronal tissue sections (~200 sections; 300 µm gap) was

304 examined in each valid case. Autofluorescence images of the tissue sections were
305 acquired through 4X objective and the Nikon B2A filter cube (ex. 450–490) for
306 anatomical reference. Regions containing labeled cells were imaged using a 10X
307 objective and the Nikon UV2A filter cube (ex. 330–380).

308 Subsequently, retrogradely labeled somata were counted using Canvas X software
309 tools. For each deposit, the fraction represented by the cells labeled in a particular
310 structure over the total of labeled neurons was calculated. It should be emphasized that,
311 given the many variables involved in the effectivity of retrograde transport labeling
312 (Schofield et al., 2007), labeled cell counts were intended here only as an indirect
313 approximation of the relative anatomical weight of the various sources of input to the
314 thalamic nuclei under investigation.

315 As a visual aid for comparison of the spatial distribution patterns of corticothalamic
316 neurons in the tangential dimension of the cerebral cortex, labeled cell somata were
317 plotted on standard flat cortex maps registered to stereotaxic coronal levels (see Figure
318 6-1). We built this map from Franklin and Paxinos (2012) coronal diagrams. For each
319 section, arc segments between cytoarchitectonic area borders measured on the section
320 diagrams were plotted along a line. The lines were then stacked in order and aligned
321 along the dorsal midline of the hemisphere (Figure 6-1). Additional details were derived
322 from CyO-stained brain sections. In the present study, the position in each section of the
323 labeled corticothalamic cells was radially projected on the pial surface and plotted along
324 its matching level line.

325

326 *Anterograde BDA labeling analysis*

327 For BDA-labeled experiments, sections were systematically examined under
328 brightfield optics. Sections containing the BDA deposit were imaged and nuclear
329 boundaries were delineated following cytoarchitectonic references provided by CyO
330 counterstain.

331 BDA-labeled axons terminals in the thalamus were analyzed and imaged using 10-
332 40X objectives. Axon arborizations were labeled in Golgi-like detail and showed
333 frequent varicose swellings. Since axonal varicosities have been shown to contain
334 presynaptic organelles and their overall size correlates with the number and/or strength
335 of synapses they establish (Rovo et al., 2012; Groh et al., 2014; Rodriguez-Moreno et
336 al., 2020), we decided to measure and compare labeled axon varicosity sizes. For this

337 purpose, varicosities were identified as such when their diameter was at least twice that
338 of the adjacent axonal segments. As a proxy of bouton size measured on two-
339 dimensional light microscope images, the major perimeter of each varicosity was
340 focused in the Z axis at 100X and delineated, and its cross-sectional (maximal
341 projection) area measured using the Polyline and Polygon tools of the Nis-Elements®
342 BR 3.2 software (Nikon). Varicosities with cross-section area below the microscope
343 resolution limit ($< 0.2 \mu\text{m}^2$) were not included in the analysis. For each glutamatergic
344 labeled projection system, 100 randomly selected varicosities were measured, and 200
345 in the case of inhibitory system (total of 2200 varicosities for all cases). Varicosity size
346 data for corticothalamic axons (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018) are included here for
347 direct comparison with other sources of input to the thalamus.

348 The location and distribution of the BDA-labeled varicosities in Po were plotted
349 using a motorized Nikon Eclipse 80i microscope with 40-60X brightfield objectives,
350 NeuroLucida controller, camera and software (v. 2020; MBF Bioscience, Williston, VT,
351 USA). The CyO counterstain was used for thalamic nuclei delineation. In each section,
352 all BDA-labeled varicosities were plotted using markers of NeuroLucida software.

353

354 ***Confocal microscope analysis***

355 Immunofluorescence analyses of axon terminals were carried using a Spectral Leica
356 TCS SP5 confocal microscope by sequentially applying argon (488 nm), diode-pumped
357 solid-state (561 nm) and/or helium–neon (633 nm) laser lines to ensure complete
358 channel separation. Regions of interest were imaged using 10X objective. In addition,
359 images of BDA-labeled axons were taken also using 20X (plus 3X digital zoom) and
360 40X objectives. For each region of interest, 10 image stacks were obtained moving the
361 sample in the Z-axis. Both image stacks and maximal projections were analyzed in
362 separate and merged channels.

363

364 ***Experimental design and statistical analysis***

365 Very small deposits of retrograde tracers often fail to label afferent pathways in
366 consistent fashion. For this reason, out of a total of fifty-two retrograde tracer injections,
367 we selected only eight injection experiments for detailed analysis (six injections in Po
368 plus two in VPM) whose deposits were confined to the nuclei of interest and had
369 produced robust retrograde labeling in distant brain regions. The retrograde labeling was

370 analyzed separately for each case, as a n=1 experiment class.

371 From the BDA-labeling experiments, we analyzed only those in which the tracer
372 deposit was confined to the intended target structure (46 injections). Comparison of
373 varicosity mean cross-sectional areas was performed using one-way ANOVA analysis
374 of variance plus T3 Dunnet's multiple comparisons as a post hoc test to identify
375 significant interactions. Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S) was used to
376 compare size distributions of varicosities between different structures. Statistical
377 analysis was computed using GraphPad Prism 5 software (San Diego, CA, USA) or
378 SPSS Statistics software (v. 24; IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Data are presented as mean
379 \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The threshold level of significance was set at $p <$
380 0.05, indicating this as (*), $p < 0.01$ as (**), and $p < 0.001$ as (***)).

Results

(-----(*Insert Figure 1 about here*)-----)

Distribution within Po of vesicular glutamate transporter-specific immunolabeled axon terminals

To compare the general distribution within Po of glutamatergic axon terminals from the cerebral cortex with those of subcortical origin, we immunostained adjacent tissue sections against either vGLUT1 or vGLUT2 (Figure 1). The vGLUT1 protein is a well-established marker of the presynaptic vesicle pools in corticothalamic terminals. In contrast, vGLUT2 protein is present in glutamatergic brainstem and spinal presynaptic terminals, but absent from corticothalamic terminals (Fujiyama et al., 2001; Oliveira et al., 2003; Bopp et al., 2017). Although most thalamic projection neurons express vGLUT2 mRNA, their protein product is selectively directed to their axon terminals, outside the dorsal thalamus (Fremeau et al., 2001; Fujiyama et al., 2001).

Immunostaining for vGLUT1 produced heavy punctate neuropil labeling across Po (Figure 1a-b). These puncta delineated, as empty spaces, cell body contours (Figure 1a1). In contrast, immunolabeling for vGLUT2 was markedly less dense overall than in the adjacent nuclei and was distributed in a variegated pattern. An extensive ventral and central portion of Po contained only very small, spherical, and weakly vGLUT2 labeled puncta. In contrast, an elongated patch in the dorsal portion of the nucleus, and smaller clusters along the border with the ventral posteromedial nucleus (VPM) contained heavily stained and larger puncta (Figure 1c-f), similar to those present in massive numbers in the adjacent VPM (Figure 1d2). The distribution and shape of these large vGLUT2 puncta-rich Po domains were consistent across animals.

(-----(*Insert Figure 2 about here*)-----)

Distribution of L5b corticothalamic axon terminals within Po

The vGLUT2 immunolabeling pattern revealed that subcortical excitatory afferent systems to Po concentrate selectively in some nucleus subdomains but are scant in others. In contrast, as both L5 and L6 corticothalamic terminals contain vGLUT1, the heavy immunolabeling precluded a reliable identification of L5 corticothalamic

414 terminals. To obtain a global and unobstructed view of the L5 axon terminals, we
415 examined the thalamus of transgenic mice Rbp4-Cre;Ai14. In these animals, abundant
416 L5b neurons in the dorsolateral cerebral hemisphere constitutively express high levels
417 of the fluorescent protein tdTomato (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2019; Hayashi et al.,
418 2021; Figure 2a-b). The thalamus of Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 animals showed a profuse plexus
419 of tdTomato-labeled varicose terminal branches and boutons in Po. However, these
420 branches were noticeably less dense or virtually absent in some small dorsal and caudal
421 Po domains (Figure 2c-f). Caudoventral Po contained a few isolated fluorescent cell
422 bodies. In addition to Po, the lateral posterior nucleus received abundant labeled
423 arborizations; in sharp contrast, fluorescent axonal arborizations were virtually absent
424 from the adjacent VPM and intralaminar nuclei.

425 A double-fluorescence analysis on Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 thalamus sections immunolabeled
426 against vGLUT2 using fluorescein-tagged secondary antibodies revealed that the
427 distribution within Po of the large glutamatergic subcortical terminals is complementary
428 to that of the L5 corticothalamic terminals (Figure 2j-l). Meanwhile, regions containing
429 small glutamatergic subcortical terminals can overlap to a variable extent with the L5
430 terminals. Overall, the dataset suggests a complex mosaic where descending L5 inputs
431 and glutamatergic spinal/brainstem inputs can converge or remain segregated in variable
432 proportions.

433

434 (-----(*Insert Figures 3 and 4 about here*)-----)

435

436 ***Distribution within Po of GABAergic axon terminals***

437 Local interneurons are essentially absent from mouse Po (Evangelio et al., 2018;
438 Jager et al., 2021), but the nucleus receives robust extrinsic GABAergic input from
439 TRN, ZI (Bartho et al., 2002), and the APT (Bokor et al., 2005). To determine if these
440 inhibitory pathways innervate Po in homogeneously fashion, we immunolabeled Po
441 sections with antibodies against the GAD65/67 isoforms, the enzymes for GABA
442 synthesis (Erlander and Tobin, 1991; Figure 3). GAD65 is localized in synaptic vesicle
443 pools of GABAergic neuron axons, whereas GAD67 is found in the cell bodies and
444 proximal dendrites as well as in many axon terminals (Esclapez et al., 1994).

445 Within Po, the GAD65/67 labeling was limited to neuropil and consisted of two
446 types of immunopositive puncta. Small ($<1 \mu\text{m}^2$) round and faintly labeled puncta were

447 found throughout the nucleus (Figure 3l). In addition, several separate focal clusters of
448 larger immunopositive puncta ($1\text{--}4\ \mu\text{m}^2$), were also present (see arrowheads in Figure
449 3a-i). These clusters were more frequent and spread in the rostral portion of Po, and
450 became limited to the dorsal third of the nucleus at more caudal levels. Additional
451 smaller groups of large puncta were also present along the border with VPM (Figure 3a-
452 c). Immunolabeling in the adjacent VPM was much heavier overall. Inspection at high
453 magnification, revealed that this VPM labeling consisted of large puncta (Figure 3j).
454 Immunolabeling with antibodies against GABA itself produced results consistent with
455 the GAD65/67 pattern just described (Figure 3-1).

456

457 *Convergence/divergence of GABAergic terminals with glutamatergic terminals of* 458 *subcortical origin or cortical L5 terminals*

459 To analyze in detail the spatial relationships between GAD65/67-positive
460 GABAergic terminals and vGLUT2-positive subcortical glutamatergic terminals, we
461 conducted a double immunolabeling analysis for these markers on the same tissue
462 sections (Figure 3d-f). We observed that the Po domains rich in large vGLUT2
463 terminals overlap to a large extent with the GAD65/67 large puncta clusters (Figure 3g-
464 i). In contrast, in the central and ventral portions of Po lacking large puncta clusters the
465 overall distribution of each marker is less specific (Figure 3r), although vGLUT2
466 terminals tend to be more abundant in medial Po regions, while GAD65/67 terminals
467 are more densely packed in the lateral part of the nucleus (see Figure 3g-i). Despite
468 close intermingling, puncta immunolabeled with each marker are almost always distinct
469 (Figure 3p-r). The double-labeling analysis thus revealed that the Po microdomains that
470 receive robust glutamatergic input of brainstem/spinal cord origin are also the
471 preferential target of the large GABAergic terminals.

472 Next, we compared the distribution within Po of the large GABAergic puncta with
473 that of L5 boutons. To this end, we immunolabeled Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 mice thalamus
474 tissue with GAD65/67 antibodies (Figure 4). This experiment revealed that the boutons
475 of L5 pyramidal cell axons preferentially target the portions of Po that contain only very
476 small GAD65/67 puncta and avoid the domains where large GAD65/67 terminals are
477 clustered.

478 Immunolabeling against vGLUT2 and GAD65/67 on the same Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 tissue
479 sections provided a direct visualization of the complex patterns of convergence/

480 segregation within Po of inputs from cortical L5, the brainstem and spinal cord, or
481 GABAergic nuclei (Figure 4j-l). Overall, the immunolabeling patterns reveal a
482 widespread innervation of Po by L5 terminals, with some small domains where
483 subcortical glutamatergic driver inputs prevail. GABAergic boutons are ubiquitous;
484 however, they preferentially show larger sizes in domains containing large subcortical
485 glutamatergic terminals.

486

487 (-----(*Insert Figure 5 about here*)-----)

488

489 ***Brain-wide retrograde tracer mapping of inputs to Po***

490 While the immunofluorescence analysis revealed that excitatory and inhibitory inputs
491 distribute unevenly within Po, it left unresolved the precise origin and local prevalence
492 of the various afferent pathways. To this end, we microinjected retrograde tracers
493 unilaterally into Po (Figure 5) and mapped the labeled cell somata across the whole
494 brain and spinal cord. We specifically chose FG and FB because of their high sensitivity
495 and the possibility of consistently delineating the injection sites. The tracer deposits
496 consisted of a core of continuously bright fluorescence with no discernible cellular
497 elements in it. This core ranged in diameter between 250–450 μm . We presume that this
498 is the region from which most or all tracer uptake and transport occurred, because all
499 deposits with a core under 250 μm of diameter failed to produce consistent retrograde
500 labeling or did not produce labeling at all. Beyond this core, there was a fading halo of
501 faint fluorescence where discrete cellular elements were recognizable. This halo probably
502 made minimal, if any, contribution to the observed labeling (Schofield et al., 2007).

503 Six cases with FG or FB deposits limited to Po were considered valid for analysis
504 (Figure 5a). Together, they covered about two-thirds of the nucleus. For comparison, we
505 also analyzed the labeling produced by two further deposits in the adjacent VPM, a FO
506 relay nucleus (Figure 5b). We reconstructed the extent of each deposit on serial
507 sections. Some deposits were completely separated (e.g.: cases Po1 vs. Po5 or Po6),
508 while others overlapped among them to variable extent.

509

510 (-----(*Insert Figures 6 and 7 about here*)-----)

511

512 ***Retrograde tracer mapping of corticothalamic inputs***

513 Retrograde tracer injections in Po or VPM labeled massive numbers of
514 corticothalamic cells (Figure 6a-d). In register with previous reports (Deschenes et al.,
515 1998; Killackey and Sherman, 2003), neurons labeled in primary somatosensory area
516 (S1) after Po or VPM injections distributed in complementary laminar patterns. The Po
517 injections labeled cells in L6b and L5b, while VPM injections labeled cells in L6a, with
518 few additional cells in L6b (Figure 6e). In addition, there were notable disparities in the
519 tangential spread across cortical areas (Figures 6g and 7). VPM injections labeled
520 corticothalamic neurons almost exclusively in ipsilateral area S1 (Figure 6f), while Po
521 injections invariably labeled cells in several cortical areas such as motor area M1 and
522 somatosensory areas S1 and S2. Additional cells were labeled by some Po injections in
523 motor area M2, and/or in the ectorhinal, insular and perirhinal areas (Figures 6g and 7).

524 Injections in different Po regions produced specific patterns of labeling across areas.
525 L6b cells were labeled in large numbers across the motor and somatosensory areas.
526 Additional L6b cells were labeled in nearby areas, as well as in the contralateral
527 hemisphere. L6a cells were labeled in large numbers always in M1, and often in area
528 S2. In contrast, labeling of L6a neurons in area S1 was relatively scarce, except in those
529 deposit located in rostral portions of the nucleus (Po1, Po2 and Po3; Figures 6g and 7).

530 Cells were labeled in L5b only in the ipsilateral hemisphere, mainly in S1, and often
531 in S2 and M1. There was rough somatotopic order in this projection; cells were labeled
532 in the macrovibrissae domain (cases Po1, Po2), snout domain (Po3), limbs domain
533 (Po4, Po6) or trunk domain of S1 (Po5, Po6) in register with the position of each
534 deposit and the known somatotopic organization of cell responses within Po (Diamond
535 et al., 1992; Figure 7b). Interestingly, the deposit in case Po5, which was centered
536 approximately in the location of the vGLUT2 rich dorsal domain of Po (Figure 1d)
537 labeled an unusually low number of L5b cells.

538

539 (-----(*Insert Figures 8 and 9 about here*)-----)

540

541 ***Retrograde tracer mapping of subcortical inputs***

542 In addition to corticothalamic neurons, tracer deposits in Po labeled multiple cell
543 populations across the diencephalon, brainstem, and spinal cord (Figures 8 and 9).
544 Sizable numbers of retrogradely labeled neurons were always found in some structures
545 known to use GABA predominantly or exclusively in their projections to the thalamus

546 such as the TRN (Figure 8a), ZI (Figure 8b) and the APT (Figure 8c). In addition,
547 labeled neurons were consistently found, in variable numbers, in subcortical regions
548 known to use mainly or exclusively glutamate in their excitatory projections to
549 thalamus, such as the SC intermediate layers (Figure 8d), the trigeminal complex
550 (Figure 8e-g) and the DCN (Figure 8h). In some experiments, cells were labeled in the
551 parabrachial complex (PB), the contralateral medial vestibular nucleus and some nuclei
552 of the brainstem reticular formation, as well as in layers I-II, V, and the lateral spinal
553 nucleus of the spinal cord (Figure 8i).

554 In contrast, the subcortical neurons labeled by the VPM injections (which were both
555 placed in the vibrissal domain of this nucleus) were present only in the trigeminal
556 complex (principal and spinal interpolaris nuclei) and TRN (Figure 9). Overall, the
557 contrasting patterns of labeling after either Po or VPM deposits are in register with the
558 notion that while VPM neurons are devoted specifically to the relay of excitatory tactile
559 signals from the face and mouth, the Po cells may integrate, along with cortical inputs
560 from L5, diverse combinations of full-body tactile, motor, nociceptive, and attention-
561 related signals conveyed via excitatory or inhibitory synapses (Yu et al., 2006; Groh et
562 al., 2014; Ahissar and Oram, 2015).

563 Comparisons between deposits that involved different Po regions reveal local
564 fluctuations in the prevalence of the various afferent systems (Figure 9). For example,
565 the deposits in the dorsal and caudal portions of the nucleus (Po4, Po5, Po6) labeled
566 sizable numbers of cells in SC, while deposits involving ventral and anterior injections
567 did not. Likewise, spinal cord and DCN cells were labeled in abundance only by
568 dorsally and medially situated deposits, whereas cells in the principal trigeminal nucleus
569 (PrV) were labeled selectively by deposits near the border with VPM. Labeling in APT
570 was robust in all cases except one limited to the ventral and central portions of the
571 nucleus (case Po3). ZI input was substantial in all cases, but more prominent in dorso-
572 caudal deposits (Po5 and Po6). In contrast, labeling in the TRN was robust in all cases.
573 Cells were labeled in the substantia nigra reticulata only in cases Po3 and Po6.

574

575 (-----(*Insert Figure 10 about here*)-----)

576

577 ***Quantitative estimation of local input convergence***

578 As a way to gauge the local convergence of different inputs, we compared the
579 numbers of cells labeled in the various structures in each retrograde tracing experiment.
580 We counted cells in the whole brain and spinal cord. To normalize for fluctuations in
581 labeling efficacy or injection volume between experiments, cells in each structure were
582 compared as percentages over labeled neuron totals. This parameter, often referred to as
583 Fraction of Labeled Neurons (FLN; Markov et al., 2011) provides an objective
584 comparison of the relative anatomical weight of the pathways. Note, however, that FLN
585 cannot be directly equated to functional impact without factoring in other parameters
586 such as the local convergence and strength of the synapses, as well as the postsynaptic
587 receptor mechanisms involved (Sherman and Guillery, 2002; Rodriguez-Moreno et al.,
588 2020).

589 First, we compared the relative contributions of the various glutamatergic input
590 pathways to the Po regions impregnated in each retrograde tracer experiment. We
591 considered this analysis relevant because the ratio of cortical vs. subcortical origins of
592 excitatory inputs is widely used for functional classification of thalamic nuclei.
593 According to this classification, FO are the thalamic nuclei that relay ascending
594 excitatory signals from the subcortical systems to the cortex, while HO nuclei send back
595 to cortex signals received from the cortex via collaterals of L5b axons. A third
596 “integrator” category has been proposed for nuclei like Po, where at least some neurons
597 receive both L5 and excitatory subcortical inputs and can integrate them in complex
598 nonlinear fashion (Groh et al., 2014). Among the excitatory pathways we compared the
599 numbers of cells labeled in pathways previously shown to drive Po neuron firing and
600 specify their information content (hence referred to as “driver” pathways; Sherman and
601 Guillery, 1996). We excluded corticothalamic L6 cells because we assume that their
602 prevalence is homogeneous across Po, and their effect on thalamus cells essentially
603 modulatory, fine-tuning variables such as temporal profile of the “driver” signals carried
604 by other pathways (Sherman, 2016; Briggs, 2020).

605 As a first step, we compared labeled cell numbers in cortical L5b vs. all
606 glutamatergic subcortical structures (Figure 10b). In the VPM control cases, subcortical
607 sensory afferents represented always over ~ 90 % of the sum cortical L5b and
608 subcortical labeled cells. Such massive prevalence may even be an underestimate, as the
609 labeled L5b cells probably represent passing axons directed to Po that were impregnated
610 at the injection site. In contrast, in Po L5b cells prevailed (~ 65–75 %) in all cases

611 except in two (24.7 % in case Po5 and 42.7 % in Po6) whose deposits overlapped the
612 vGLUT2-rich domain in central-dorsal Po. Overall, these findings show that while most
613 of Po is robustly innervated by L5b, all parts of the nucleus receive a sizable number of
614 inputs from subcortical excitatory structures. The central and dorsal vGLUT2-rich
615 domain of Po receives a proportion of subcortical excitatory inputs in a proportion
616 nearing that of the “FO-relay” VPM.

617 Cortical L5b input to Po originated mainly from S1, finding at least 63 % of all L5b
618 labeled cells in this area and up to 98.3 % in case Po2 (74.1 % of all putative “driver”
619 inputs; Figure 10d). Other Po domains also receive a significant percentage of L5b
620 inputs from other cortical areas, such as the motor cortex (Po1, 16.5 %; Po5, 19.5 %) or
621 S2 (Po3, 20.8 %).

622 The trigeminal complex was labeled in all cases, but most robustly in experiments
623 placed in rostral and ventral levels of Po. This input arose always from the SpV (oralis
624 and interpolaris nuclei present 12.3–29.3 % of subcortical cells), and, in the deposits
625 injected in the anterior half of Po, also from PrV (Figure 10e). Cells in the intermediate
626 layers of SC were most numerous in those experiments with deposits in dorsal and
627 caudal Po, being the majority (56.4 %) among the glutamatergic subcortical cells
628 labeled in case Po6 (32.3 % of all putative “driver” inputs; Figure 10e). Dorsal column
629 nuclei cells were labeled in all cases, yet they were markedly more numerous when the
630 deposit overlapped the position of the dorsal vGLUT2-rich domain of Po (30.6 % in
631 Po4 and 21.6 % in Po5 of all subcortical cells). Likewise, spinal cord neurons were a
632 small but consistent fraction of the subcortical glutamatergic afferent mix. The most
633 abundant labeling was observed in cases located in dorsomedial Po (up to 23.5 % of all
634 subcortical cells in Po5 and Po6; Figure 10e).

635 Likewise, we compared the proportion of retrogradely labeled cells within the group
636 of structures known to innervate the thalamus via GABAergic axons (Figure 10c). TRN
637 was robustly labeled in all Po injection cases, although its prevalence among
638 GABAergic inputs fluctuated widely (32.8–82.7 %) depending on the presence or
639 absence of other inputs. Projections from APT were labeled after every retrograde tracer
640 injection in Po. Their prevalence among other GABAergic inputs ranged from 8.0 %
641 (case Po3, involving ventral Po) to 49.6 % (case Po4 involving dorsal-central Po).
642 Neurons projecting to Po from the ZI were likewise labeled by every Po injection. They
643 fluctuated between 5.6–29.7 %, and were most abundant after injections involving

644 dorsal and caudal Po portions. Remarkably, we found a positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.75$)
645 between the number of labeled cells in the extra-reticular inhibitory structures with the
646 subcortical structures (Figure 10f), but not with number of L5b cells ($R^2 = 0.17$; Figure
647 10g). In striking contrast with Po, VPM received GABAergic inputs exclusively from
648 TRN (Figure 10c).

649

650 (-----(*Insert Figure 11 about here*)-----)

651

652 ***Distribution within Po of afferent pathways***

653 Retrograde tracing experiments informed about the sources and relative weight of the
654 various input pathways to Po but did not delineate with precision the domains targeted
655 or spared by each pathway. To this end, first we compared the fluorescent protein
656 axonal labeling produced in Po by relatively large associated adenovirus vector (AAV)
657 injections placed in some structures identified in the retrograde study (Figure 11; Allen
658 Institute for Brain Science, 2011; Paxinos and Franklin, 2012; Oh et al., 2014; Harris et
659 al., 2019).

660 This analysis provided several important insights. First, it showed that APT axons
661 arborize heavily in the most rostral Po levels (at about \sim AP -1.50), but far less so at
662 more caudal levels, where they concentrate mainly in the dorsolateral corner of the
663 nucleus (Figure 11a-b). Remarkably, the dense APT terminal axon arborizations do not
664 spread to other nuclei and display an uneven, clustered pattern. Second, viral vector
665 injections in ZI consistently labeled axons targeting only the dorsal half of Po. Unlike
666 APT, the ZI axon arborizations extend dorsally to the nearby laterodorsal and lateral
667 posterior nuclei (Figure 11c-d). Vector injections in the spinal trigeminal nucleus label
668 axons in ventral and lateral portions of Po and provide substantially more profuse axon
669 arborizations in VPM (Figure 11e-f). Finally, axons from the intermediate/deep layers
670 of the SC innervate only a dorsal fringe of Po but arborize densely in the adjacent lateral
671 posterior nucleus (Figure 11g-h).

672

673 (-----(*Insert Figure 12 and 13 about here*)-----)

674

675 To analyze the fine morphology of axon arborizations and complete the delineation
676 of their target territories, we made BDA microinjections in the various subcortical

677 structures that innervate Po (Figures 12 and 12-1). Some BDA injections were placed in
678 the same structures labeled in the Allen Brain Connectome Dataset (Allen Institute for
679 Brain Science, 2011). The distribution within Po of these BDA-labeled axon terminals
680 was consistent with the viral transfection data and added topographic detail (Figures 13
681 and 13-1).

682 Moreover, double fluorescence labeling for vGLUT2 and BDA confirmed that the
683 projections from both the Gr and Cu nuclei (n=5) target the isolated vGLUT2-rich
684 domain in the central and dorsal portion of Po in a focused manner. There they have
685 large boutons ($> 1 \mu\text{m}^2$) immunopositive for this transporter (Figure 12a-d). DCN axons
686 target the dorsal and central region of the nucleus. The distribution of labeled axon
687 varicosities after BDA injections limited to the Cu or Gr indicate that axons from the Cu
688 nucleus former terminate in more dorsal and lateral sectors of Po than those from the
689 latter (Figure 13a-b).

690 Likewise, boutons labeled from BDA injections in the principal (n=4) and spinal
691 trigeminal nuclei (n=8) were immunopositive for vGLUT2 and formed small clusters in
692 the lateral border of the nucleus, near VPM (Figure 12e-h). Anterograde labeling
693 experiments show that the trigeminal axons remain relatively scattered within ventral
694 Po, being very scant in the dorsomedial third of the nucleus. Some trigeminal terminals
695 mass into clusters of large boutons along the lateral border of Po (Figures 13c-d and 13-
696 1a-c).

697 In addition, the labeling produced in Po by large BDA injections in the intermediate
698 layers of the SC (n=2) innervate the dorsal third of Po, but not the ventral part of the
699 nucleus (Figures 12-1i-j and 13e). On the other hand, deposits in the parabrachial
700 complex (PB; n=2) innervate mainly the ventral and caudal portion of Po (Figures 12-
701 1g-h and 13-1d). Finally, BDA deposits in the vestibular complex (n=3) show scarce
702 axonal arborization in Po, with just a few varicosities (data not shown).

703 Vector transfection datasets did not include experiments involving the spinal cord.
704 We examined the labeling produced in Po by large BDA injections (n=2) in the central
705 spinal gray matter laminae at about the third cervical level and found labeled axons in
706 the dorsomedial portion of Po (Figures 12-1k-l and 13f) a region matching that reported
707 to respond to tactile stimulation of the limbs and trunk (Diamond et al., 1992). Spinal
708 cord terminals are more abundant in the caudal half of the nucleus.

709

710 (-----(*Insert Figure 14 about here*)-----)

711

712 Small deposits in different portions of the TRN (n=4), labeled richly branched and
713 relatively focal arborizations in Po. The position of these arborizations varied in register
714 with that of the TRN injections. For example, a BDA deposit in a central domain of
715 TRN labeled axonal arborizations in dorsolateral Po, along the border with VPM
716 (Figure 14a-c), while a deposit in a ventral domain of TRN labeled axons only in the
717 ventral region of Po (Figure 14d-f).

718 The distribution of APT (n=2) and ZI (n=8) BDA-labeled axon terminals within Po
719 was consistent with the viral transfection data (Figure 14-1). APT axons are present
720 across most of Po and leave dense clustered arborizations in the rostral region of the
721 nucleus (Figure 14-1a-c). ZI axons distributed mainly in rostral Po and more sparsely at
722 caudal and ventral levels (Figure 14-1d-i). The position of these arborizations generally
723 aligns with the heavy concentrations of large GAD65/67 puncta observed in this region
724 (Figure 2).

725 Overall, the labeled axon arborization patterns in the viral vector tracing datasets or
726 BDA microinjections are consistent with the immunolabeling and retrograde tracing
727 mapping results. Together, they delineate several subdomains within Po, each
728 containing a specific combination of two or more overlapping excitatory (L5, DCN,
729 trigeminal, SC) or predominantly inhibitory (APT, ZI) long-range input systems. The
730 input combinations might thus impinge on particular Po projection neurons (Groh et al.,
731 2014) while not on others. In contrast, the glutamatergic corticothalamic L6 terminals
732 and GABAergic TRN terminals appear to cover Po homogeneously and in rough
733 topographic fashion; hence, they probably reach all Po neurons with similar prevalence.

734

735 *Axonal varicosity sizes of the input pathways*

736 In glutamatergic and GABAergic axon terminals, varicosities reflect local
737 accumulations of mitochondria and synaptic vesicle pools at presynaptic sites (which
738 may be single or multiple). Hence, varicosity size provides an indirect indication of
739 important functional parameters such as synapse release probability and strength
740 (Sherman and Guillery, 2002; Halassa and Acsady, 2016; Rodriguez-Moreno et al.,
741 2020). Interestingly, some of the afferent inputs to Po investigated in the present study
742 such as the glutamatergic L5b corticothalamic (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018) or the

743 mainly GABAergic ZI and APT axons (Halassa and Acsady, 2016) had been previously
744 shown to have unusually large varicosities in their terminal axon branches.

745 To compare in systematic fashion varicosity sizes across the various input systems
746 targeting Po and as an indirect indicator of their synaptic strength, we measured and
747 compared their maximal projection areas in axons labeled by BDA injections in
748 different subcortical structures (Figures 12 and 12-1). For comparison, we included in
749 this analysis a previously published dataset of bouton sizes from BDA deposits located
750 in L5b, L6a and L6b (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018).

751

752 (-----(*Insert Figure 15 about here*)-----)

753

754 First, we compared the axonal varicosities from cortical and subcortical
755 glutamatergic structures (Figure 15). For each structure, we analyzed both the frequency
756 of size distribution (Figure 15e) and the mean size (Figure 15f). Statistical data
757 comparisons are summarized in Table 15-1. We found that the mean sizes of
758 varicosities in axons originating from L6a and L6b in the barrel field of the primary
759 somatosensory cortex (S1BF; $0.60 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $0.58 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}^2$, respectively) were
760 always significantly smaller than those originated in L5b ($2.42 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{m}^2$) or
761 subcortical structures (T3 Dunnett's, $p < 0.05$ for all comparisons) and had a
762 significantly different frequency in size distribution (K-S, $p < 0.001$ for all
763 comparisons). The varicosities from nucleus Gr, Cu, ventrolateral region of the
764 principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-VL) and the interpolaris portion of the spinal
765 trigeminal nuclei (SpVI), as well as the deep intermediate layers of the SC did not differ
766 significantly in size from cortical L5b varicosities. The varicosities in the caudal portion
767 of the spinal trigeminal nuclei (SpVC; $4.16 \pm 0.34 \mu\text{m}^2$) were significantly bigger than
768 those from L5b (T3 Dunnett's, $p = 0.003$). Other glutamatergic axons had significantly
769 smaller axonal varicosities than cortical L5b, including some trigeminal subnuclei
770 (oralis portion of the spinal trigeminal nuclei, SpVO, and dorsomedial part of the
771 principal trigeminal nuclei, PrV-DM), parabrachial complex and axons from the central
772 laminae of the spinal cord.

773

774 (-----(*Insert Figure 16 about here*)-----)

775

776 Varicosity sizes were likewise measured and compared among GABAergic axon
777 populations (Figure 16), analyzing the frequency of size distribution (Figure 16e) and
778 the mean size (Figure 16f). We included in this analysis the varicosities from TRN
779 axons in VPM. Statistical data are summarized in Table 16-1. The analysis revealed that
780 the largest varicosities are those arising from APT ($1.96 \pm 0.09 \mu\text{m}^2$) and ZI ($1.80 \pm$
781 $0.08 \mu\text{m}^2$). No significant differences were found between APT and ZI varicosities in
782 the overall distribution of sizes. Both populations included, in addition to a large
783 number of relatively small varicosities, a consistent fraction of unusually large
784 varicosities (Figure 16f). Axonal varicosities in TRN axons across most of Po were
785 significantly smaller ($0.84 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}^2$; T3 Dunnet's, $p < 0.001$ for all comparisons) and
786 had a significantly different frequency in size distribution (K-S, $p < 0.001$). In contrast,
787 the terminals from this nucleus were much larger along the lateral border of Po, near
788 VPM ($1.83 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{m}^2$) as well as inside VPM ($1.58 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{m}^2$; T3 Dunnet's, $p <$
789 0.001).

790 (-----(*Insert Figure 17 about here*)-----)

791

792 **Discussion**

793

794 We mapped the origin, intranuclear distribution and axon varicosity sizes of the
795 excitatory and inhibitory input pathways to Po, a representative HO nucleus of the
796 thalamus. Results reveal that while some pathways (L6, TRN) innervate all regions of
797 Po with similar abundance, other pathways (L5, DCN, trigeminal, SC, spinal cord, APT,
798 ZI) concentrate in some regions but are absent from others, creating within Po a
799 complex mosaic of partly overlapping domains (Figure 17).

800

801 ***Cortical inputs to Po***

802 The cortex is the main source of inputs to Po. In consonance with the massive
803 presence of vGLUT1 terminals, which are almost exclusively of cortical origin
804 (Graziano et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2018), our retrograde tracer Po injections invariably
805 labeled large numbers of cortical cells in L6a, L6b and L5b.

806 The corticothalamic pathways originated in L6 are by far the largest contingent of
807 cells innervating Po. The overall effect of these projections has been shown to be
808 essentially modulatory, fine-tuning variables of thalamic neuron firing (Sherman, 2016;
809 Briggs, 2020). L6b cells were labeled consistently in areas S1, S2, M1 and ectorhinal
810 cortices, which, interestingly, are the regions innervated by Po axons (Ohno et al., 2012;
811 Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018). In contrast, L6a inputs to Po arise mainly from M1
812 and S2, consistent with the notion that L6a inputs arise from those areas that Po
813 innervates in *feedforward* laminar pattern (L4-3), while L6b inputs arise from those
814 innervated in *feedback* pattern (L5a and L1; Ohno et al., 2012; Casas-Torremocha et al.,
815 2019).

816 In register with previous observations, we show that L5b inputs to Po originate
817 mainly from ipsilateral S1, with a clear topographic order (Diamond et al., 1992;
818 Alloway et al., 2003; Sumser et al., 2017). L5b inputs have been shown to be able to
819 drive Po cell firing, determining the information content of their output (Reichova and
820 Sherman, 2004; Theyel et al., 2010; Mease et al., 2016). Some Po regions can receive
821 convergent L5b inputs from separate cortical areas in consonance with recent
822 observations by Sampathkumar et al., (2021), while other zones receive L5b inputs

823 exclusively from S1 (cases Po2, Po4). Remarkably, labeled L5b cells were unusually
824 scant in case Po5, resembling the pattern observed in the VPM injection cases. As the
825 deposit in this case matched the position of a vGLUT2-rich and Rbp4-Cre: Ai14
826 neuropil-poor domain located midway along the dorsal third of Po, these observation
827 raises the possibility that some neurons in that Po domain may have a “FO-like”
828 character.

829

830 *Subcortical inputs to Po*

831 Our data show that Po receives sizable direct input connections from structures in the
832 diencephalon, brainstem and spinal cord known to use excitatory (DCN, trigeminal
833 sensory complex, and SC), or mainly inhibitory neurotransmitters (TRN, APT, ZI). The
834 labeling patterns observed with antibodies against vGLUT2, or GAD65/67 reveal that
835 some of these connections are very unevenly distributed within Po, both in terms of
836 local abundance and puncta size.

837 *DCN and spinal cord inputs:* We show that Po receives a relatively small but robust
838 projection from the contralateral DCN, targeting the dorsal and central region of the
839 nucleus, in a pattern equivalent to that described in the rat Po (Villanueva et al., 1998).
840 They form large boutons, similar in size to those from cortical L5b, that abound in the
841 vGLUT2-rich dorsal Po domain.

842 We show that direct spinal inputs reach the dorsomedial portion and caudal half of
843 the nucleus. The mean size of the varicosities in the spinal axons is relatively small, in
844 consonance with previous observations in rats (Iwata et al., 1992). As spinothalamic
845 projection neurons contain exclusively vGLUT2 mRNA (Persson et al., 2006), it is
846 possible that many of the vGLUT2-positive puncta observed in the dorsomedial corner
847 of Po correspond to spinothalamic axon terminals.

848 *Trigeminal inputs:* Our data show that the trigeminal complex projections are
849 scattered across ventral and central Po but scant in the dorsomedial third of the nucleus.
850 Trigemino-thalamic neurons mostly express vGLUT2 mRNA (Graziano et al., 2008; Ge
851 et al., 2014). Ventral Po shows only sparse vGLUT2 labeling, in consonance with the
852 sparse distribution of the anterogradely labeled terminals. In contrast, some trigeminal
853 terminals mass into clusters of large vGLUT2-positive boutons along the lateral border
854 of Po. Studies in rats have shown that Po receives most of its ascending inputs from
855 SpVI and that these axons form large varicosities (Veinante and Deschenes, 1999;

856 Pierret et al., 2000; Lavallee et al., 2005). In register with their bouton morphology,
857 trigeminal axons have been shown to drive Po cells with short latency, as typical driver
858 inputs; however, their effect on Po cells is suppressed most of the time by the powerful
859 GABAergic inputs from ZI and APT (Trageser and Keller, 2004; Lavallee et al., 2005).

860 *Superior colliculus inputs:* Our data indicate that the intermediate layers of the SC
861 innervate the dorsal third of Po, but not the ventral part of the nucleus. SC varicosities
862 in Po are relatively large. Colliculo-thalamic terminals in Po have been recently shown
863 to be able to drive Po neurons (Gharaei et al., 2020).

864 *Anterior pretectal nucleus and zona incerta inputs:* In consonance with previous
865 studies in rats (Bartho et al., 2002; Bokor et al., 2005), we show that APT and ZI axons
866 reach most of Po and leave dense clustered arborizations in the rostral region of the
867 nucleus. These arborizations align with the clumps of large GAD65/67 puncta present in
868 this region. Boutons in APT and ZI axons are on average larger than other putatively
869 GABAergic Po inputs, and a fraction of them are unusually large. The GABAergic
870 axons have been reported to terminate as large boutons on proximal dendrites, able exert
871 powerful sustained inhibition of the Po cells (Trageser and Keller, 2004; Lavallee et al.,
872 2005; Wanaverbecq et al., 2008; Halassa and Acsady, 2016). The notable dispersion in
873 the sizes of the APT and ZI axon varicosities thus suggests that our BDA injections
874 labeled both GABAergic and glutamatergic projection axons. Our data show that the
875 ventral part of Po receives few APT or ZI projections, consistent with reports the ZI
876 inhibitory effects are found only in a fraction of Po neurons, particularly in those
877 located in rostral and dorsolateral regions of the nucleus (Lavallee et al., 2005).

878 *Thalamic reticular nucleus inputs:* TRN inputs regulate gain control and rhythm
879 genesis, modulating the rate of thalamic neurons spikes, while preserving their
880 information content (Halassa and Acsady, 2016). Every region of Po is innervated by
881 numerous TRN axons. The small terminals from these richly arborized axons (Pinault et
882 al., 1995) are probably the main contributor to the faint, fine-grained and ubiquitous
883 neuropil of GAD65/67-positive terminals observed in Po.

884 VPM receives GABAergic inputs exclusively from TRN. However, the GAD65/67-
885 positive neuropil labeling in VPM is clearly stronger than in Po. This may reflect the
886 fact that the TRN axons innervating Po show three times less varicosities than those
887 targeting VPM (Pinault and Deschenes, 1998). In addition, TRN boutons in VPM and
888 the lateral border of Po display significantly larger varicosities than in the rest of Po.

889 These varicosities may represent branches from VPM-targeting axons or a specific TRN
890 subpopulation (Lam and Sherman, 2007; Halassa et al., 2014; Li et al., 2020).

891

892 *The input landscape of HO nuclei*

893 In contrast with the uniform, monoculture-like appearance of inputs in the adjacent
894 VPM, the neuropil landscape of the Po inputs is a variegated mosaic of segregated but
895 partly overlapping domains (Figure 17). This pattern is directly visualized, to some
896 extent, in the multi-labeling overlays for GABAergic, L5 and vGLUT2
897 immunofluorescent labeling. It must be noted, however, that not all Po inputs seem to
898 be heterogeneously distributed, as L6 and TRN axons are consistently found across Po.
899 Both pathways are known to have modulatory effects (excitatory or inhibitory) on
900 signal transmission. In contrast, most or all pathways with synapses powerful enough to
901 determine cell spiking, either in excitatory or in inhibitory fashion (Sherman, 2012;
902 Halassa and Acsady, 2016) distribute unevenly across Po.

903 Given the arrangement and size of the various neuropil domains, it is intriguing to
904 consider that mouse Po neurons have bushy dendritic trees of about 250 μm in diameter
905 (Figure 17; see also Ohno et al., 2012). As a result, a majority of Po cells, and
906 particularly those situated near domain borders, may receive powerful inputs from more
907 than one source, in graded combinations. In fact, there is experimental evidence that
908 such convergence occurs. For example, some cortical L5b and trigeminal synaptic
909 boutons target the same Po neurons and their signals can be nonlinearly integrated in the
910 thalamic cells to code for temporal relationships between tactile and cortical signals
911 (Groh et al., 2014; Ahissar and Oram, 2015). Likewise, direct convergence onto single
912 Po cells of L5 inputs from two separate cortical areas has been recently demonstrated
913 (Sampathkumar et al., 2021). By favoring the emergence of unique signal integration
914 modules, the richly diverse input combinations to HO nuclei neurons may expand the
915 computational range of thalamocortical interactions.

916

917 **Author contributions**

918 DCT, CP and FC designed the experiments,
919 ZM, AHS and SH made some early observations and provided Rbp4-Cre;Ai14
920 transgenic mice brains,
921 DCT and MRT performed the experiments,
922 DCT, MRT and CP analyzed the data,
923 DCT, MRT, CP and FC prepared the figures and tables,
924 DCT and FC wrote the paper with input from CP, MRT, AHS, SH, LP and ZM.

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Figures

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1151 **Figure 1**

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1154 **Figure 2**

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1159 **Figure 4**

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1161 **Figure 5**

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1164 **Figure 6**

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1169 **Figure 8**

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● An occasional cell ■ Few cells ■ Numerous cells ■ Very abundant cells

1177 **Figure 11**

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1179 **Figure 12**

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1185 **Figure 14**

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1189 **Figure 15**

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1192 **Figure 16**

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1198 **Table 1**

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Brain region	AP	ML	DV	Tip diameter	Current	Time (min)	Cycle (s
				(μm)	intensity (μA)		ON/OFF)
TRN	-1.5	± 2.2	-3.0	5–7	0.2–0.3	40–45	1
ZI	-2.1	± 1.5	-4.0	6–8	0.3–0.5	40–45	1
APT	-2.8	± 1.1	-2.6	8–12	0.8–1	40–45	1
SC	-3.3	± 1.0	-2.0	8–10	0.8–1	20–30	1
Gr	-0.2*	± 0.5	-0.2*	15–20	1–2	20–30	7
Cu	-0.5*	± 1.0	-0.2*	15–20	1–2	20–30	7
PB	-5.0	± 1.1	-2.5	10–15	1–2	20–30	7
MVe	-5.8	± 0.9	-3.0	10–15	1–2	30–40	7
PrV-VL	-5.4	± 1.9	-3.7	10–15	1–2	30–40	7
PrV-DM	-5.4	± 1.9	-3.2	10–15	1–2	30–40	7
SpVO	-5.8	± 1.8	-3.7	10–15	0.8–1	30–40	1
SpVI	-7.2	± 1.8	-3.0	10–15	0.8–1	30–40	1
SpVC	-7.7	± 1.8	-2.7	10–15	0.8–1	30–40	1
Spinal cord	C1-C2	± 0.5	-0.3	12–14	1.5–2	20–30	7

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1202 **Table 2**

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Antibodies	Manufacturer	Dilution
Guinea pig anti-vGLUT1 polyclonal antibody serum	Chemicon®, Merck Millipore. Cat. n°: AB5905	1:2000
Guinea pig anti-vGLUT2 polyclonal antibody serum	Sigma-Aldrich. Cat. n°: AB2251-I	1:2000
Biotinylated goat anti-guinea pig polyclonal IgG	Vector Laboratories. Cat. n°: BA-7000	1:200
Rabbit anti-biotin polyclonal antibody serum	Abcam. Cat. n°: AB53494	1:500
Rabbit anti-red fluorescent protein (RFP) polyclonal antibody serum	MBL International. Cat. n°: PM005	1:500
Rabbit anti-gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)	Sigma-Aldrich. Cat. n°: A2052	1:500
Rabbit anti-glutamate decarboxylase 65 & 67 (GAD65/67) polyclonal antibody serum	Chemicon®, Merck Millipore. Cat. n°: AB1511	1:100
Rabbit anti- GAD65/67 polyclonal antibody serum	Sigma-Aldrich. Cat. n°: ABN904	1:100
AlexaFluor® 488-conjugated goat anti-guinea pig polyclonal IgG	ThermoFisher. Cat. n°: A-11073	1:200
AlexaFluor® 568-conjugated goat anti-rabbit polyclonal IgG	ThermoFisher. Cat. n°: A-11011	1:200
AlexaFluor® 647-conjugated goat anti-rabbit polyclonal IgG	ThermoFisher. Cat. n°: A-21244	1:200

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1206 **Extended Figure 3-1**

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1209 **Extended Figure 6-1**

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1213 **Extended Figure 12-1**

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1215 **Extended Figure 13-1**

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1218 **Extended Figure 14-1**

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1220

1221

1222 **Extended Table 15-1**

	Mean ± sd	Test	Gr												
Gr	2.50 ± 0.21	Anova	-												
		K-S	-	Cu											
Cu	3.04 ± 0.31	Anova	1.000	-											
		K-S	0.261	-	PrV-DM										
PrV-DM	1.42 ± 0.19	Anova	0.016 *	0.001 **	-										
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	PrV-VL (Center Po)									
PrV-VL (Center Po)	0.93 ± 0.08	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.826	-									
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.344	-	PrV-VL (Border Po)								
PrV-VL (Border Po)	3.59 ± 0.31	Anova	0.290	1.000	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-								
		K-S	0.069	0.031 *	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	SpVO							
SpVO	1.09 ± 0.08	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	1.000	1.000	0.000 ***	-							
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.005 **	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	SpVI						
SpVI	1.78 ± 0.14	Anova	0.327	0.021 *	1.000	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.004 **	-						
		K-S	0.020 *	0.008 **	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.001 **	0.000 ***	-	SpVC					
SpVC	4.16 ± 0.34	Anova	0.004 **	0.726	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	1.000	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-					
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.001 **	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.099	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	SC				
SC	1.93 ± 0.15	Anova	0.913	0.116	0.951	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	1.000	0.000 ***	-				
		K-S	0.193	0.013 *	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.002 **	0.000 ***	0.443	0.000 ***	-	Spinal cord			
Spinal cord	1.40 ± 0.13	Anova	0.001 **	0.000 ***	1.000	0.238	0.000 ***	0.985	0.989	0.000 ***	0.547	-			
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.008 **	0.008 ***	0.000 ***	0.069	0.008 **	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	PB		
PB	1.23 ± 0.08	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	1.000	0.571	0.000 ***	1.000	0.066	0.000 ***	0.005 **	1.000	-		
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.005 **	0.005 **	0.000 ***	0.020 *	0.069	0.000 ***	0.008 **	0.794	-	L5b S1BF	
L5b S1BF	2.42 ± 0.23	Anova	1.000	1.000	0.074	0.000 ***	0.204	0.000 ***	0.751	0.003 **	0.998	0.013*	0.000***	-	
		K-S	0.031 *	0.099	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.001 **	0.000 ***	0.008 **	0.000 ***	0.008 **	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	L6a S1BF
L6a S1BF	0.60 ± 0.02	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.005 **	0.014 *	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	-
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	L6b S1BF
L6b S1BF	0.58 ± 0.03	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.003 **	0.007 **	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	1.000 -
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	0.261 -

1223

1224 **Extended Table 16-1**

	Mean ± sd	Test	ZI				
ZI	1.80 ± 0.08	Anova	-				
		K-S	-	APT			
APT	1.96 ± 0.09	Anova	0.997	-			
		K-S	0.779	-	TRN (center Po)		
TRN (center Po)	0.84 ± 0.03	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-		
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	TRN (VPM)	
TRN (VPM)	1.58 ± 0.06	Anova	0.546	0.020 *	0.000 ***	-	
		K-S	0.052	0.027 *	0.000 ***	-	TRN (border Po)
TRN (border Po)	1.83 ± 0.06	Anova	1.000	0.999	0.000 ***	0.074	-
		K-S	0.010 *	0.014 *	0.000 ***	0.005 **	-

1225

Figure legends

1226

1227

1228 **Figure 1. Distribution within Po of vesicular glutamate transporter-specific** 1229 **immunolabeled axon terminals.**

1230 **(a, b)** Microphotographs showing in different coronal sections of Po the distribution of
1231 terminals marked by immunohistochemistry against the glutamate vesicular transporter
1232 type 1 (vGLUT1). High-magnification details are in shown in **a1**. **(c-f)**

1233 Microphotographs showing in different coronal sections of Po the distribution of
1234 terminals marked by immunohistochemistry against the glutamate vesicular transporter
1235 type 2 (vGLUT2). High-magnification details showing larger vGLUT2 terminals in
1236 dorsal domains (**d1**) and in the border with the ventral posteromedial nucleus (VPM;
1237 **d2**), smaller vGLUT2 terminals in the lateral portion of Po (**d3**) and domains with
1238 almost absence of these terminals in the ventral portion (**e1**). AP: bregma level in mm.
1239 Scale bars: a-f 250 μm ; a1, d1-d3 and e1 30 μm .

1240

1241 **Figure 2. Distribution within Po of L5 corticothalamic and vGLUT2-positive axon** 1242 **terminals.**

1243 Double immunofluorescence labeling against tdTomato and vGLUT2 in Rbp4-Cre;Ai14
1244 mice tissue. **(a)** Epifluorescence image of a representative coronal section of the
1245 somatosensory cortex of an Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 mouse. **(b)** Higher magnification of the
1246 boxed region in (a), showing the location detail of tdTomato-positive cells in a column
1247 of S1BF. Scale bars: a 250 μm , b 100 μm . **(c-l)** High-resolution confocal images show
1248 the distribution of tdTomato (L5 axons) in three different coronal sections of Po **(c-f**;
1249 magenta), vGLUT2 **(g-i**; green), and its merge **(j-l)**. Note that the distribution within Po
1250 of the large glutamatergic subcortical terminals is complementary to that of the L5
1251 corticothalamic terminals. A high-magnification detail of L5 axonal varicosities in Po is
1252 shown in **d**. AP: bregma level in mm. Scale bars: a, c, e-l 250 μm ; b 100 μm ; d 15 μm .

1253

1254 **Figure 3. Distribution within Po of glutamatergic subcortical and GABAergic axon** 1255 **terminals.**

1256 High-resolution neuropil images showing the distribution of puncta labeled by
1257 immunohistochemistry against glutamate decarboxylases 65 and 67 (GAD65/67; **a-c**;
1258 magenta), vGLUT2 **(d-f**; green), and its merge **(g-i)**. Arrowhead indicates focal clusters

1259 of larger immunopositive puncta. High-magnification details of GAD65/67 (**j-l**),
1260 vGLUT2 (**m-o**) and its merge (**p-r**) are shown for VPM, Po dorsal and Po ventral
1261 domains. AP: bregma level in mm. Scale bars: a-i 250 μ m; j-r 10 μ m.

1262

1263 **Figure 4. Distribution within Po of glutamatergic subcortical, GABAergic axon**
1264 **terminals and L5 axons.**

1265 High-resolution confocal images showing the distribution of vGLUT2 (**a-c**; green),
1266 GAD65/67 (**d-f**; blue), tdTomato (L5 labeled cells; **g-i**; magenta) and its merge in
1267 Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 coronal sections (**j-l**). Note that regions enriched in vGLUT2 and
1268 GAD65/67 are roughly complementary to those receiving L5 cortical axons. AP:
1269 bregma level in mm. Scale bars: 250 μ m.

1270

1271 **Figure 5. Location of retrograde tracer deposits.**

1272 Location of the six retrograde tracer deposit in Po (**a**; Po1, FB; Po2- Po6, FG) and in
1273 VPM (**b**; VPM1, FB; VPM2, FG). Epifluorescence images showing the center of the
1274 deposits are shown in the left. Deposits were drawn overlaying microphotographs in all
1275 Po coronal sections of Franklin and Paxinos atlas (2012), and they were represented
1276 with halo and central zone. Anteroposterior, dorsoventral and mediolateral coordinates
1277 are indicated above, on the right or below, respectively. Adjacent serial sections were
1278 stained with cytochrome oxidase histochemistry to delimit thalamic nuclei. Scale bars:
1279 250 μ m.

1280

1281 **Figure 6. Origins of corticothalamic projections to VPM and Po.**

1282 Epifluorescence microphotographs showing retrogradely stained neuron somatas in a
1283 coronal section of the cerebral cortex from a deposit located in VPM (**a**) and in Po (**b**).
1284 (**c**) High-magnification detail of L5b corticothalamic labeled cells. (**d**) High-
1285 magnification detail of L6 corticothalamic labeled cells. (**e**) Cortical column details
1286 showing the corticothalamic input patterns in S1BF, S1mv, M1 and S2. (**f-g**) Location
1287 of ipsilateral labeled cortical neurons: Separate maps are used to represent L5b
1288 (magenta), L6a (blue) and L6b (green) cells. Dots represent relative labeled cell
1289 densities. Panels f and g represent the labeling in VPM1 and Po3 cases, respectively.
1290 Abbreviations: BF, barrel field; Cg1, cingulate cortex; Ect, ectorhinal area; FL,
1291 forelimb; HL, hindlimb; Ins, insular area; J, jaw; M1-M2, motor area; mv, micro

1292 vibrissae; Prh, perirhinal area; S1, primary somatosensory area; S2, secondary
1293 somatosensory area; Tr, trunk; ULp, upper lip. Scale bars: a, b 250 μm ; c, d 25 μm ; e
1294 150 μm .

1295

1296 **Figure 7. Corticothalamic projections to different Po domains.**

1297 (a) Direct comparison of the relative position of the tracer deposits. (b) Location of
1298 ipsilateral retrogradely labeled cortical neurons in cases Po1, Po2, Po4, Po5 and Po6.
1299 Conventions as in Figure 6f-g.

1300

1301 **Figure 8. Subcortical inputs to Po.**

1302 Epifluorescence images showing retrogradely labeled cell bodies (arrows) in the
1303 ipsilateral reticular thalamic nucleus (TRN; **a**), zona incerta (ZI; **b**), anterior pretectal
1304 nucleus (APT; **c**), superior colliculus (SC; **d**), and contralateral principal (PrV; **e, f**) and
1305 interparietal spinal (SpVI; **i**) trigeminal nuclei, gracilis nucleus (Gr; **h**) and dorsal horn
1306 of spinal cord (**i**). High-magnification details are shown as insets. A coronal section
1307 sketch is included, for reference. Other abbreviations: CuR, cuneatus nucleus, rotundus
1308 part; DMSpV, dorsomedial spinal trigeminal nucleus; DpG, deep gray layer; Gr: gracilis
1309 nucleus; InG, intermediate gray layer; InWh, intermediate white layer; Op, optic tract;
1310 PrV-DM, principal trigeminal nucleus, dorsomedial part; PrV-VL, principal trigeminal
1311 nucleus, ventrolateral part; ZId, dorsal division of ZI; ZIv, ventral division of ZI. Scale
1312 bars: a-i 250 μm , insets 25 μm .

1313

1314 **Figure 9. Summary of subcortical projections to Po and VPM.**

1315 Graphic summary of the relative abundance of retrogradely labeled cells in the
1316 forebrain, midbrain, hindbrain, and spinal cord in all cases analyzed in this study.
1317 Ipsilateral (I) and contralateral (C) projections are represented separately for each case.
1318 Relative abundance of labeled cells is represented by shades of gray. Asterisks indicate
1319 the glutamatergic structures (red) and GABAergic structures (blue) that were quantified
1320 (Figure 10).

1321

1322 **Figure 10. Quantitative estimation of input convergence in Po.**

1323 (a) Location of the retrograde tracer deposits. (b) Percentage comparison of cells
1324 sending putatively “driver” excitatory inputs to Po (cortical layer 6 cells are not

1325 included). Cortical L5b (colored in void) vs. subcortical structures (superior colliculus +
1326 sensory brainstem + spinal cord) colored in gray shade. Total number of labeled cells is
1327 indicated above. (c) Percentage comparison of cells labeled among the four structures
1328 sending putatively inhibitory inputs to Po. Anterior pretectal nucleus (APT, void),
1329 substantia nigra pars reticulata (SNR, black), zona incerta (ZI, dash) and reticular
1330 thalamic nucleus (TRN, gray shade). Total number of labeled cells is indicated above.
1331 (d) Percent comparison of L5b cells labeled in each cortical area over the total of
1332 putatively excitatory inputs (cortical+ subcortical). (e) Percent comparison of labeled
1333 cells in each subcortical structure over the total of putatively excitatory inputs (cortical+
1334 subcortical). Structures showing less than 2 % of the total labeled cells were grouped as
1335 “Other”. (f) Correlation analysis between the absolute numbers of cells retrogradely
1336 labeled in subcortical structures providing Po long-range inhibitory inputs (APT + ZI +
1337 SNR) vs. those labeled in subcortical structures providing putatively excitatory inputs.
1338 (g) Correlation analysis between the absolute numbers of cells retrogradely labeled in
1339 subcortical structures providing long-range inhibitory inputs vs. cells labeled in cortical
1340 L5b. Correlations are indicated by linear regression as well as by the coefficient of
1341 correlation (R^2). Other abbreviations: DCN, dorsal column nuclei; PrV, principal
1342 trigeminal complex; S1, primary somatosensory cortex; S2, secondary somatosensory
1343 cortex; SC, superior colliculus; SpV, spinal trigeminal complex; VC, vestibular
1344 complex.

1345

1346 **Figure 11. Viral vector tracing of projections to Po from subcortical regions.**

1347 Single two-photon tomography image samples taken from experiments in which viral
1348 vectors able to drive the expression of high levels of fluorescent protein were injected in
1349 some of the structures that originate long-range Po inputs. Mouse Connectivity
1350 Projection dataset (Allen Institute for Brain Science, 2011). Injections sites in the
1351 anterior pretectal nucleus (APT; **a**), the zona incerta (ZI; **c**), the interpolaris spinal
1352 trigeminal nucleus (SpVI; **e**), or the superior colliculus (SC; **g**). Coronal section images
1353 showing fluorescently labeled axons in Po are shown in **b**, **d**, **f**, and **h**. AP: bregma level
1354 in mm. Abbreviations: CL, central lateral nucleus; PC, paracentral nucleus; PF,
1355 parafascicular nucleus; VL, ventrolateral nucleus; VPM, ventral posteromedial nucleus;
1356 ZId, dorsal zona incerta; ZIv, ventral zona incerta; DpG, deep gray layer; InG,
1357 intermediate gray layer; InWh, intermediate white layer; Op, optic tract. Scale bars: a, c,

1358 e, g 1000 μm ; b, d, f, h 500 μm . Experiments from the Mouse Connectivity Projection
1359 dataset can be found in
1360 <http://connectivity.brain-map.org/projection/experiment/278401778> (a-b), 301539438
1361 (c-d), 272738620 (e-f), and 128001349 (g-h).

1362

1363 **Figure 12. Axons in Po labeled by BDA injections in glutamatergic subcortical**
1364 **structures.**

1365 Microphotographs showing location of BDA deposits in the cuneatus (Cu; **a**) and
1366 gracilis (Gr; **c**) nuclei, ventrolateral part of principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-VL; **e**), or
1367 pars caudalis of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVC; **g**). Cytochrome oxidase
1368 counterstain. Confocal images of double immunofluorescence labeling within the Po of
1369 vGLUT2 terminals (green) and BDA axons (red) from Cu (**b**), Gr (**d**), PrV-VL (**f**) and
1370 SpVC (**h**). Insets are represented as white squares. High magnification detail is shown
1371 for each case. Arrowhead indicates BDA axonal varicosities immunopositive for
1372 vGLUT2. AP: bregma level in mm. Scale bars: a, c, e, g 250 μm ; b, d, f, h 100 μm ;
1373 insets 25 μm .

1374

1375 **Figure 13. Axonal varicosities in Po labeled by BDA injections in glutamatergic**
1376 **subcortical structures.**

1377 Schematic representation of the location of axonal varicosities in Po and adjacent
1378 thalamic nuclei, plotted from the anterograde axonal labeling of BDA micro-
1379 iontophoretic injection sites in ventrolateral region of principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-
1380 VL; **a**), the caudalis part of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVC; **b**), gracilis nucleus
1381 (Gr; **c**), cuneatus nucleus (Cu; **d**), cervical spinal cord (**e**) and superior colliculus (SC;
1382 **f**). Individual axonal varicosities in Po are represented as red circles, and axonal
1383 varicosities outside Po are represented in gray color. Abbreviations: Ang, angular
1384 thalamic nucleus; LD, laterodorsal nucleus; LP, lateral posterior nucleus; LPM, lateral
1385 posterior nucleus, medial part; LPL, lateral posterior nucleus, lateral part; PC,
1386 paracentral nucleus; PF, parafascicular nucleus; VL, ventrolateral nucleus; VPM,
1387 ventral posteromedial nucleus. AP: bregma level in mm. Scale bar: 250 μm .

1388

1389 **Figure 14. Axons labeled in Po by BDA injections in the thalamic reticular nucleus.**

1390 BDA microdeposits in a dorsal (**a**) and ventral (**c**) portion of the thalamic reticular
1391 nucleus (TRN). Axonal arborizations in Po are represented in panels **b** and **e**,
1392 respectively. Cytochrome oxidase histochemistry counterstain. **c** and **f**. Individual
1393 axonal varicosities in Po are represented in red ink; those outside Po are drawn in gray.
1394 Scale bars: a, c, d, f 250 μm ; b, e 100 μm .

1395

1396 **Figure 15. Varicosity size in axons from subcortical glutamatergic structures.**

1397 Microphotographs showing examples of axonal varicosities from L6a (**a**), spinal
1398 trigeminal nucleus pars oralis (SpVO; **b**), cortical L5b (**c**) and ventrolateral part of the
1399 principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-VL; **d**) in Po. Scale bars: 10 μm . (**e**) Size distribution
1400 of axonal varicosities in Po labeled different cortical and subcortical glutamatergic
1401 structures. Axonal varicosities were grouped into discrete intervals according to their
1402 maximal cross-sectional area. (**f**) Box-plot diagram showing axonal varicosity sizes of
1403 all glutamatergic structures innervating Po. Other abbreviations: SpVC, caudalis spinal
1404 trigeminal nuclei; Cu, cuneatus; Gr, gracilis; SC, superior colliculus; SpVI, interpolaris
1405 spinal trigeminal nucleus; PrV-DM, dorsomedial part of the principal trigeminal
1406 nucleus.

1407

1408 **Figure 16. Varicosity size in axons from GABAergic structures.**

1409 Microphotographs showing examples of axonal varicosities from the inhibitory
1410 structures that innervate Po: anterior pretectal nucleus (APT; **a**), zona incerta (ZI; **b**) and
1411 thalamic reticular nucleus (TRN; **c-d**). Scale bar: 10 μm . (**e**) Size distribution of axonal
1412 varicosities grouped into discrete intervals according to their maximal cross-sectional
1413 area. (**f**) Box-plot diagram showing axonal varicosity sizes.

1414

1415 **Figure 17. Input landscapes of the Po nucleus neuropil.**

1416 Cartoon diagram of Po regions targeted by the various input systems. The delineations
1417 are based on the combined immunolabeling and tracing data in this study. Higher color
1418 saturation is used to indicate regions containing more densely packed terminals. Empty
1419 areas indicate regions containing few or no terminals. (**a**) Thalamic reticular nucleus
1420 (TRN) and layer 6 (L6) corticothalamic inputs cover Po in homogeneous fashion. (**b**)
1421 Cortical L5b inputs. (**c**) Territories targeted by axons from dorsal column nuclei (DCN),
1422 the spinal cord, trigeminal complex or the intermediate/deep layers of the superior

1423 colliculus (SC). (d) Territories targeted by zona incerta (ZI) and anterior pretectal
1424 nucleus (APT). For comparison, a drawing of a typical mouse Po neuron
1425 somatodendritic domain (Porrero et al., 2016) is included at the same scale. Scale bar:
1426 250 μm .

1427

1428 **Table 1. Injection parameters applied to selectively inject BDA in brain regions**
1429 **that innervate Po.**

1430 Stereotaxic coordinates for the anteroposterior (AP), mediolateral (ML) and
1431 dorsoventral (DV) levels respect to bregma used for each structure are indicated.
1432 Asterisks indicate distance to the obex. Tip diameter (μm), current intensity (μA) time
1433 (min) and cycle (s ON/OFF) are indicated for each case. Abbreviations: TRN: thalamic
1434 reticular nucleus, ZI: zona incerta. APT: anterior pretectal nucleus; SC: superior
1435 colliculus, middle & deep layers; Gr: gracilis nucleus; Cu: cuneatus nucleus; MVe:
1436 medial vestibular nucleus; PB: parabrachial nuclei; PrV-VL: principal trigeminal
1437 nucleus, ventrolateral portion; PrV-DM: principal trigeminal nucleus, dorsomedial
1438 portion; SpVO: spinal trigeminal nucleus, oral division; SpVI: spinal trigeminal
1439 nucleus, interpolar division; SpVC: spinal trigeminal nucleus, caudal division.

1440

1441 **Table 2. List of antibodies used in this study.**

1442 For each antibody, manufacturer, catalogue number and dilution used are indicated.

Extended data legends

1443

1444

1445 **Extended Figure 3-1. Distribution of GABA immunolabeled neuropil in Po.**

1446 Distribution within Po of terminals marked by immunohistochemistry against GABA.

1447 Three different coronal levels are shown (**a-c**). Arrowhead indicates focal clusters of

1448 GABAergic immunopositive axons. Note that the immunolabeling is heavier in the

1449 adjacent ventral posteromedial (VPM). Other abbreviations: PC, paracentral nucleus;

1450 PF, parafascicular nucleus. AP: bregma level in mm. Scale bars: a-c 250 μ m.

1451

1452 **Extended Figure 6-1. Generation of an isometric surface map of mouse somatic** 1453 **motor and sensory areas.**

1454 (**a, b**) This map was created by aligning all the pial contours of Franklin and Paxinos

1455 (2012) coronal section diagrams as parallel lines along the dorsal midline “watershed”

1456 of the cerebral hemisphere (black arrowheads and dashed black line on the map). (**c**)

1457 Flat map detail of the areas used in the subsequent figures to represent the

1458 corticothalamic labeling. Abbreviations: A1: primary auditory area; Cg: cingulate

1459 cortex; Ect: ectorhinal area; FrA: frontal association; INS: insular (granular +

1460 dysgranular) cortex; M1: primary motor area; M2: secondary motor area; S1: primary

1461 somatosensory area; S2: secondary somatosensory area; V1: primary visual area.

1462

1463 **Extended Figure 12-1. Axonal arborizations in Po arising from subcortical** 1464 **glutamatergic structures.**

1465 BDA deposits in the dorsomedial region of principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-DM; **a**),

1466 oralis (SpVO; **c**) and interpolaris (SpVI; **e**) part of spinal trigeminal nucleus,

1467 parabrachial nuclei (PB; **g**), superior colliculus (SC; **i**) and a low cervical level of spinal

1468 cord (**k**). Details of the axonal arborizations in Po arising from PrV-DM (**b**), SpVO (**d**),

1469 SpVI (**f**), PB (**h**), SC (**j**) and spinal cord (**l**) are shown. Cytochrome oxidase

1470 counterstain. AP: bregma level in mm. Scale bars: a, c, e, g, i, k 250 μ m; b, d, f, h, j, l

1471 100 μ m; insets 25 μ m.

1472

1473 **Extended Figure 13-1. Axonal varicosities labeled from subcortical glutamatergic** 1474 **structures.**

1475 Location of axon varicosities labeled by BDA injections in the principal trigeminal
1476 nucleus (PrV-DM, **a**); pars oralis of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVO, **b**); pars
1477 interpolaris of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVI; **c**); and parabrachial complex (PB;
1478 **d**). Each red dot represents a varicosity in Po; varicosities outside Po are shown in gray
1479 ink. Abbreviations: Ang, angular thalamic nucleus; LD, laterodorsal nucleus; LP, lateral
1480 posterior nucleus; LPM, lateral posterior nucleus, medial part; LPL, lateral posterior
1481 nucleus, lateral part; PC, paracentral nucleus; PF, parafascicular nucleus; VL,
1482 ventrolateral nucleus; VPM, ventral posteromedial nucleus. AP: bregma level in mm.
1483 Scale bar: 250 μ m.

1484

1485 **Extended Figure 14-1. Axonal arborizations in Po labeled by BDA injections in**
1486 **GABAergic structures.**

1487 BDA deposits in the anterior pretectal nuclei (**a**) and in the dorsal (ZId; **d**) and ventral
1488 (ZIV; **g**) portion of the zona incerta. Axon arborizations in Po labeled by each of these
1489 experiments **b**, **e** and **h**, respectively. Cytochrome oxidase counterstain. AP: distance to
1490 bregma in mm. Correspondence drawings of the axonal varicosities locations in each
1491 section are shown in **c**, **f** and **i**. Individual axonal varicosities in Po are represented as
1492 red circles, and axonal varicosities outside Po nucleus are represented in gray color.
1493 Scale bars: a, c, d, f, g, i 250 μ m; b, e, h 100 μ m; insets 25 μ m.

1494

1495 **Extended Table 15-1. Quantitative analysis of varicosity size from glutamatergic**
1496 **structures.**

1497 Comparison of varicosity mean cross-sectional areas was performed using one-way
1498 ANOVA analysis of variance plus T3 Dunnet's multiple comparisons as a post hoc test
1499 to identify significant interactions. Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S) was
1500 used to compare size distributions of varicosities between different structures.
1501 Data from L5b, L6a and L6b were previously published in Hoerder-Suabedissen et al.,
1502 2018.

1503

1504 **Extended Table 16-1. Quantitative analysis of varicosity size from GABAergic**
1505 **structures.**

1506 Comparison of varicosity mean cross-sectional areas was performed using one-way
1507 ANOVA analysis of variance plus T3 Dunnet's multiple comparisons as a post hoc test

1508 to identify significant interactions. Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S) was
1509 used to compare size distributions of varicosities between different structures.
1510